

Performance modelling of an ultra-high bypass ratio geared turbofan

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, the main modelling aspects for setting up an Ultra-High Bypass Ratio (UHBR) Geared Turbofan (GTF) engine performance model with Variable Pitch Fan (VPF) and/or bypass Variable Area Nozzle (VAN) are first described. Next, a multi-point design (MPD) structure is presented considering performance requirements and thermal, structural and aerodynamic constraints at top-of-climb, take-off and cruise conditions. Using the MPD approach, multi-parametric studies are then carried out to generate a design space of engine cycles according to the specified targets and limits which are representative of a UHBR GTF in a narrow body aircraft for short range applications with an Entry Into Service (EIS) of 2025.

Keywords: Ultra-High Bypass Ratio; Geared Turbofan; Variable Geometry; Multi-point Design

NOMENCLATURE

ACARE	Advisory Council for Aviation Research and Innovation in Europe	LTO	Landing and Take-off
BPR	Bypass Ratio	MPD	Multi-Point Design
CR	Cruise	OPR	Overall Pressure Ratio
EIS	Entry Into Service	PCM	Pitch Change Mechanism
FPR	Fan Pressure Ratio	PR	Pressure Ratio
GTF	Geared Turbofan	SFC	Specific Fuel Consumption
HP	High Pressure	SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
HPC	High Pressure Compressor	TO	Take-Off
HPT	High Pressure Turbine	ToC	Top-Of-Climb
LP	Low Pressure	UHBR	Ultra-High Bypass Ratio
LPC	Low Pressure Compressor	VAN	Variable Area Nozzle
LPT	Low Pressure Turbine	VPF	Variable Pitch Fan
LSBH	Last Stage Blade Height		

Symbols

Dtip	Tip Diameter	Tt4	Combustor Exit Total Temperature
eff	Isentropic Efficiency	Tt41	HP Turbine Equivalent Rotor Inlet Total Temperature
effPoly	Polytropic Efficiency	Tt45	LP Turbine Inlet Total Temperature
FN	Net Thrust	VQid	Ideal Nozzle Velocity Ratio
NH	HP Spool Rotational Speed	W1	Engine Inlet Mass Flow Rate
NLG	Fan Rotational Speed	Wcool	Cooling Air Mass Flow Rate
R	Pertaining to Rotor	WF	Fuel Flow Rate
S	Pertaining to Stator	Ws	Specific Flow
Tm	Metal Temperature	ΔA	Change in Nozzle Area
Tt3	Compressor Discharge Temperature	$\Delta\beta$	Change in Blade Pitch Angle

1.0 INTRODUCTION

In order to achieve the short term ACARE Vision 2020 [1] and the long term ACARE SRIA 2050 [2] environmental targets for aviation, several innovative steps are needed both at the aircraft and engine level as well as in air traffic management and operations. According to Sieber [3], the contribution of engines towards meeting the near term objectives (EIS of 2025) is expected to be fulfilled through ducted turbofans with ultra-high bypass ratios (UHBR), high overall pressure ratios (OPR) and small cores. UHBR engines will offer improved overall efficiency through increases in both propulsive and thermal efficiencies [4] and are expected to provide a significant noise level reduction [5]. In order to transform UHBR's low specific fuel consumption (SFC) to fuel burn benefit, the development and maturation of a number of key enabling technologies is still required.

For fixed thrust requirements and with current technologies and materials, the increase in fan diameter needed to achieve the ultra-high BPR values envisaged for EIS of 2025 (>15), implies increased powerplant weight and nacelle drag that may outweigh any SFC improvements. So, the extent to which lightweight, short, low drag nacelles and compact, lightweight turbomachinery components can be materialized will dictate an upper limit of the BPR value [6]. Another constraint is the minimum available/allowable ground clearance, especially if engine retrofitting is considered. Core technologies are crucial if UHBR performance benefits are to be achieved at reasonable fan diameters. According to Tong et al. [7], UHBR engines with an EIS of 2025 are expected to be equipped with compressor and turbine active flow and clearance control, lean burn combustor and Ceramic Matrix Composites (CMC) turbine.

In a conventional direct-drive turbofan, increasing BPR to ultra-high levels will result to a significant increase in LPT stage number [8] and LP shaft torque [9]. According to Bijewitz et al. [10] the direct drive turbofan is becoming unattractive for BPR greater than 13, a value in accordance with the results presented by Guynn et al. [11]. Introducing a reduction gear between the fan and the LPC/LPT shaft, allows each component to rotate at its optimum speed in terms of efficiency, stage loading, stage count and noise. Furthermore, increased LP speed makes it possible to distribute the pressure ratio differently between the LP and HP compressors [4].

The low fan pressure ratios ($FPR < 1.45$) associated with UHBR engines require some form of variable geometry to avoid fan stability issues at low flight speeds when the nozzle un-chokes and the fan operating line is displaced to reduced mass flows and closer to surge line [12]. Two types of variable geometry are commonly proposed [9]: the variable area bypass nozzle (VAN) and the variable pitch fan (VPF). The VAN increases the fan nozzle throat area at low flight speeds to allow more airflow to pass through it thus moving the fan operating point to higher flow capacities and away from surge, while the fan map (and surge line) is not affected. The VPF is raising the surge pressure ratio for a given mass flow without affecting the position of the fan operating line. The effect of pitch change on the fan map is similar to the one due to inlet guide vanes. Reducing the pitch for take-off moves the surge line to higher pressure ratios while the fan swallowing capacity decreases ([13], [14]). According to McKay and Barlow [6], for engine BPRs in the range of 12-15, a VAN will be used for managing fan stall and flutter margins at off-design conditions. For BPRs beyond 25, they claim that the VAN system weight will become prohibitive, while an area increase over 30% would be needed. Krishnan et al. [15] assuming constant VPF weight and a 10% weight penalty for the VAN concluded that the crossover point at which VPF becomes necessary is in the range of 20 to 27 BPR. Finally, it should be mentioned that the simultaneous use of VPF and VAN has also been considered, e.g. in [13] and [16].

With regards to the optimum values of BPR/FPR for a GTF engine reported in the literature, the verdict depends on the technology level assumptions and the metrics considered. For example, the results published by Daggett et al. [17] define the optimal BPR for a GTF engine as 14.3 ($FPR = 1.45$), for both small and large aircrafts. According to the authors, this value can be obtained without the necessity of a VAN. The results presented by Guynn et al. [18] in 2011 indicate that no single engine configuration provides the best performance across all of the metrics. The engine for minimum block fuel is a GTF with $FPR = 1.5$ and $BPR = 14.7$ and for minimum block NO_x is a GTF with $FPR = 1.6$ and $BPR = 12.4$, both without VAN. On the other hand, the optimum engine in terms of noise and LTO NO_x emissions is a VAN GTF with $FPR = 1.4$ and $BPR = 17.6$. In the multi-objective optimization employed by Berton and Guynn [19], block fuel is minimized by a low $FPR (= 1.36)$ UHBR GTF with a VAN while a moderate $FPR (= 1.48)$ GTF without a VAN is identified as an excellent compromise engine design across all the metrics. Apart from fuel efficiency, weight and environmental metrics, the final engine design would also be defined by its initial price, maintenance costs and reliability characteristics, as reported by Bennett [20].

It is apparent that in order to explore the design space of a variable geometry UHBR GTF engine, a multi-disciplinary approach is required consisting of models capable of capturing the influence of the technologies necessary to meet the full potential of UHBR engines in the near future. The objective of this work is to contribute towards the development of advanced modelling and simulation capabilities for the preliminary design analysis of UHBR engines by combining and integrating models and processes in a commercial software environment. The methodological approach is first described in detail, followed by an application example where the effect of technology assumptions on the design space of a generic UHBR engine is examined.

2.0 METHODOLOGY

The engine preliminary design phase is a highly iterative process involving a number of engineering disciplines such as thermodynamics, aerodynamics, stress and mechanical design. A modular approach is thus required comprising robust, accurate and fast execution models and allowing for any gas turbine engine configuration, any discipline and any level of model fidelity to be simulated. Visualization of the results is also essential in order to help the analyst to quickly evaluate the impact of the design parameters on the overall engine design. In addition, the ability to define and combine different calculation types in a consistent and user-friendly manner is highly desirable in order to reduce model setup time. Within the research community, the TERA [21] and EDS [22] tools have been developed with this modular philosophy in mind but both contain a variety of models from disparate sources some of which are proprietary in nature while the level of integration is not fully transparent and requires an expert user to set up the model and calculation chain.

The tool used in this study is the commercial simulation environment PROOSIS [23]. The tool has architecture with clearly defined limits between modelling and simulation. Its non-causal object-oriented language (C++ like) allows the user to develop component models for any physical system that can be described with differential-algebraic equations. Components and their interfaces (Ports) are typically organized in libraries according to their discipline and are associated to a fully customizable icon through which the public attributes of the component can be accessed in a graphical user interface. Components from one or more libraries can be combined together in a schematic diagram to form a system for which one or more mathematical models can be defined through a set of wizards that guide the user in the selection of the appropriate boundary and algebraic variables of the problem. The last step is to define one or more simulation cases using either built-in wizards for a large variety of calculations or the programming language in order to construct more complex calculations.

Finally, a simulation case can be executed in batch or through a monitor application that allows various types of graphs and tables to be defined. PROOSIS and its TURBO library of gas turbine components [24], has been used to model contemporary aircraft engine configurations ([25]) while advanced engine concepts have been studied by extending the TURBO library with the required new components or functionalities ([26]-[28]). Some examples of the tool's multi-fidelity and multi-disciplinary capabilities can be found in References [29]-[30].

In addition to developing component models relevant to a UHBR engine configuration such as VPF and VAN, the present study integrates at the same modelling level and within the same simulation environment, engine thermodynamic performance, turbomachinery component aerodynamics, flow path generation and weight estimation, all within a multi-point design calculation that considers simultaneously a set of discrete operating points in the engine flight envelope. To the authors' knowledge, a study that includes all of these elements and is not relying on proprietary information has not been reported before in the public literature. In the following subsections, the modelling aspects and the overall calculation process is described.

2.1 Engine performance

To enable UHBR engine performance modelling in PROOSIS (v3.8.0), the existing TURBO library (v4.0.1) is extended with models for VPF and VAN components by taking advantage of the tool's abstraction and inheritance capabilities. Specifically, a VPF component model is created by extending the existing Fan component model functionality, so that the variation of blade pitch angle and its effect on fan performance can be simulated. First, an input port is added to allow the change (from a datum value) in blade pitch angle ($\Delta\beta$) to be specified externally either through a control system or directly as a user-defined input value. To account for the effect of varying the pitch angle on fan performance, $\Delta\beta$ is added as an additional independent parameter in the bypass and core characteristics thus leading to 3D maps in a similar way to that described in [27]. For this reason, the bypass and core characteristics presented in [14] are digitized, smoothed (using Smooth-C [31]) and converted to the PROOSIS compatible map format. During the engine design point calculation, the maps used are scaled accordingly. This implementation allows also the simulation of a conventional fan by simply setting $\Delta\beta=0$. The use of a multi-map approach for modelling a VPF was also adopted by Krishnan et al. [15]. Concerning the VAN, the modelling of the existing TURBO library Nozzle component is extended by adding an input port representing the change in nozzle area (ΔA). Based on the value of ΔA , the design (or reference) nozzle area is scaled accordingly. Similarly to the VPF, the value of ΔA can either be provided through a control system or directly as a user-input value. The effect of VAN on engine performance is established by changing the nozzle area. The same component can be used to simulate a fixed area nozzle by keeping $\Delta A=0$ throughout the engine operation.

2.2 Component Aerodynamics

In the context of a design calculation, the isentropic or polytropic efficiency of turbomachinery components is an input. Typically, efficiency values are assumed at the outset of the cycle analysis and their values are updated or validated following the aerodynamic design of the components [32]. Performance and aerodynamic design calculations are fully coupled in the present study by developing new compressor and turbine components with aerodynamic design functionality that directly inherit the entire mathematical models of the corresponding ones used for performance simulations. In this way, a consistent modelling, single step calculation is achieved between the two disciplines with no data transfer required between them while the existing functionality of the components for performance calculations is not affected.

For both compressor and turbines, a stage-by-stage design approach is followed for establishing the stage and overall component efficiencies. The number of stages can be either an input parameter or determined from design requirements. From the known cycle parameters at the component inlet and a specified hub-to-tip ratio and Mach number, the flow annulus dimensions at the inlet are established. The annulus shape is then specified by selecting constant mean, tip or hub diameter design. Alternatively, a mean diameter distribution can be defined in which case the outlet hub-to-tip ratio is also an input. From knowing the mean diameter of each stage and the rotational speed, the blade tangential speed can be found. In the case of compressors, a blockage factor is employed to obtain effective dimensions from geometric ones while inter-stage bleeds are taken into account when establishing the mass flow rate at the inlet of each stage. At stage level, it is assumed that mean diameter and axial velocity (and hence flow coefficient) remain constant. Across the compressor, the user can specify a linear distribution of either axial velocity or flow coefficient between inlet and outlet. The work performed by each compressor stage can be specified by selecting either constant work coefficient or constant stage enthalpy rise or a distribution of stage enthalpy rise expressed as a fraction of the component total enthalpy change. The user can specify either a known reaction distribution along the compressor or a distribution for the absolute velocity angle at the stage inlet. The calculation of the dimensionless velocity triangles at the mean radius is performed according to Lewis [33]. A free-vortex flow approximation is used to calculate all the necessary stage parameters at the two blade span extremes, the hub and the tip. This enables some critical parameters from

aerodynamic or structural point of view to be monitored such as diffusion factors at rotor tip or stator hub, relative Mach number at rotor tip, rim and tip tangential blade speeds, etc. Stage polytropic efficiency is calculated from stage pressure ratio using a correlation from Glassman [34].

For turbine aerodynamic design, the methodology described by Glassman [35] is implemented but extended for variable gas properties and accounting for the introduction of cooling flows. As for compressors, constant work coefficient, constant stage enthalpy rise or a distribution of stage enthalpy change expressed as a fraction of the component total enthalpy change can be specified. The stage velocity diagram is also an input (symmetrical, impulse, zero exit swirl or user-defined). Stage isentropic efficiency is expressed in terms of stage flow and stage work coefficients using correlations from Aungier [36].

For the fan, the technology trend curves of fan adiabatic efficiency and design tip speed versus design FPR presented by Felder et al. [37] are integrated in the VPF component model. These curves were originally developed by the Aerospace System Design Laboratory at Georgia Tech University and have been updated by NASA to reflect technology readiness date of 2025.

2.3 Turbine Cooling Calculations

In the case of multi-stage turbines, the stage-by-stage aerodynamic calculations described in the previous section take into account the introduction of the turbine cooling flows at the relevant row (stator or rotor) and their mixing with the main gas path flow. This allows for the accurate calculation of the cooling flow working potential in the turbine rotor which is used by the equivalent single stage efficiency model [38] employed in the corresponding thermodynamic calculations. For a given cooling flow fraction, stator and rotor metal temperatures are established with the methodology described by Wilcock et al. [39] by specifying the values of just five cooling technology constants, namely the cooling flow factor K_{cool} , the internal cooling efficiency η_{int} , the film cooling effectiveness ϵ_f , the metal Biot number Bi_{met} and the thermal barrier coating (TBC) Biot number Bi_{TBC} . In the definition of the rotor blade cooling effectiveness ϵ_0 , the relative total temperature of the mainstream gas is used based on the calculated velocities from the aerodynamic computations while the cooling air temperature drop due to pre-swirling is accounted through specifying a swirling factor. To account for temperature non-uniformities in the combustor outlet flow, the gas temperature is increased (for both stator and rotor) using a combustion pattern factor K_{comb} . Finally, a user-defined factor corrects the stage efficiency calculated in the previous step for the presence of cooling flows in the stage stator and rotor.

2.4 Flow Path & Weight Estimation

Having calculated the radial coordinates of the turbomachinery components, the next step is to establish the axial dimensions to allow not only estimating component length but also plotting the corresponding flow path contour. The methodology employed is primarily based upon calculating the blade axial chord lengths at the blade hub and tip. Axial sizing of a fan assumes user-defined values for axial aspect ratios while axial chords are assumed constant in the radial direction. Other inputs include the core hub and tip and the bypass hub and tip angles and the non-dimensional axial distances between the rotor and the two stator rows. For compressors and turbines, first and last stage aspect ratios and blade spacing are specified while intermediate stage quantities are calculated through simple linear interpolation. Assuming constant true blade chord in the radial direction, hub and tip axial chords are obtained from the corresponding setting angles computed from the mean line flow angles and the free-vortex flow approximation.

From the calculated component dimensions, the weight of the fan, fan duct, compressors, combustor, turbines, structural supports and control/accessories are estimated using the correlations by Sagerser et al. [40]. The gearbox weight is estimated using an empirical correlation suggested by Hendricks and Tong [41] expressing gearbox weight as a function of gear ratio and maximum delivered output power. The weight of the Pitch Change Mechanism (PCM) of a VPF is expressed as a fraction of the total fan weight. The VAN weight is usually modelled via a 10% penalty compared to an equivalent fixed-area nozzle (e.g. [11], [15], [18], [19], [42]). Since in the current study the weight of the engine nozzle is not explicitly calculated, it is assumed that the area changing mechanism's additional weight is only a small portion of the engine's total weight (<2% from data presented in [42]). Finally, the nacelle weight is calculated from the simplified correlation proposed by Jackson [43] using the expressions suggested in [10] to estimate cowl diameter and length.

2.5 Installed performance

As discussed earlier, UHBR SFC benefits on fuel burn can be negated due to increased engine weight and nacelle drag. Installation effects can be studied by coupling the engine model with an aircraft performance model and running a full mission analysis as for example reported in References [19], [44] and [45]. An aircraft performance model with the same qualitative features as the other modules of this study is currently under development and hence this type of analysis will be the subject of a future publication. An alternative approach that has been used in [7] and [10] is to use fuel burn exchange factors. Although there are values available in the

public domain for SFC and weight trade factors (e.g. in [7] and [44]), no such values have been found for nacelle drag (or tip diameter) relevant to UHBR engines. Thus installation effects are taken into account in this study using the simplified approach described by Cumpsty and Heyes [46] where drag nacelle is expressed in terms of specific thrust sFN , flight velocity V_f and an empirical constant k (typical value is 0.04) while the effect of total engine weight Wt_{eng} (i.e. including nacelle weight) is assumed to contribute to overall aircraft drag. Hence, a corrected net thrust FN_{cor} value can be obtained from Eq. 1, where LqD is the aircraft lift-drag ratio:

$$FN_{cor} = FN \cdot \left(1 - k \cdot \frac{V_f}{sFN}\right) - Wt_{eng}/(LqD) \quad \dots (1)$$

The installed SFC is then simply WF/FN_{cor} where WF is the actual fuel flow rate.

2.6 Integrated Design Calculation

The aircraft engine design process needs to take into account performance requirements and constraints that exist in different operating points throughout the flight envelope. For this reason, a Multi-Point Design (MPD) approach is required in order to create a design space populated only with feasible candidate designs as described for example by Schutte et al. [47]. In the present study, the MPD method is implemented over an engine model comprising of components with performance, aerodynamics, flow path generation and weight estimation functionalities. A single step approach is thus established involving different disciplines and multiple operating points. A schematic representation of the entire process is depicted graphically in Figure 1 for the case of two operating points within the MPD structure.

Figure 1 Integrated Design Procedure

The first step in the MPD process is to specify which variables will be calculated during the design procedure (independent variables). These can be either model boundaries at the level of each operating point considered in the MPD analysis (e.g. fuel-to air ratio) or component attributes at global level (e.g. map scaling factors, areas, cooling flow fractions, component areas). This implies that the mathematical model must be extended with a corresponding number of closure equations in order to be solvable. These equations can be defined in any number of operating points and are expressed in terms of equalities or groups of inequalities. In the context of PROOSIS, an inequality group is equivalent to an equation, as one of the relations behaves as an active equality, while the rest of them act as inequalities. In the more advanced type of inequalities that can be defined (saturated group), the sign of the main equation when it becomes an inequality depends on which inequality has become active as an equation (e.g. lower or upper bounding inequality). A typical closure equation is the required value for net thrust at each operating point. Other closure equations could include the value for fan pressure ratio at top-of-climb, the values for polytropic or isentropic efficiency of turbomachinery components at cruise and the values for HPT blade metal temperatures at take-off. A representative group of inequalities may consist of the value for overall pressure ratio (OPR) at top-of-climb (main equality) provided that

compressor exit temperature at take-off is below an upper limit (1st inequality) and HP compressor last stage blade height is above a lower limit (2nd inequality). Both restrict the maximum value of OPR so they make the main equality upper bounded when any of them is violated and becomes equality. Other inequalities could involve aerodynamic and structural constraints such as the relative tip Mach number at compressor first stage at ToC and the rim speed at the same spool turbine last stage at TO both of which limit the spool rotational speed. The calculation process consists of a global solver controlling the vector of independent variables (global design variables and local algebraic variables for each operating point) that will satisfy the entire set of closure equations (residues vector) which is obtained from solving the algebraic problem at each operating point for the corresponding extended mathematical formulation (model internal plus local closure equations for each point). An important aspect of this procedure is the correct initialization of all the independent variables. In the present implementation, this initialization step is based on solving a mathematical representation of the engine thermodynamic model at a single point (typically the map scaling point) for the selected values of design parameters.

3.0 APPLICATION EXAMPLE

Using the turbomachinery components that combine thermodynamic cycle analysis with 1D aerodynamic efficiency prediction, flow path generation and weight estimation, a schematic diagram of a UHBR GTF engine is constructed as shown in Figure 2. The engine model includes both a VPF and a VAN and has a planetary gearbox (GBX) connected between the VPF and LP compressor. Cooling and sealing air for the HPT is extracted at HPC exit conditions from duct D30. This cooling flow is always a fixed percentage of HPC exit flow. The equivalent single stage turbine efficiency model [38] is implemented with fixed percentage of the cooling flow doing work in the HPT rotor. Similarly, an HPC inter-stage bleed is used to provide cooling/sealing air for the LPT. A handling bleed is also included at the exit of LPC in duct D24 with the flow returning to the bypass duct (R15). Fixed shaft and gearbox transmission losses are applied. A customer bleed can be specified at the inlet, exit or any stage of HPC while customer power extraction from either the HP or the LP spools can be specified.

Figure 2 UHBR Engine Schematic Diagram in PROOSIS

Off-design performance of all turbomachinery components is obtained from suitable maps scaled accordingly during the design calculation. Specifically, for the core and bypass maps of the VPF, the characteristics presented in [14] for the reference, +4° and -4° pitch angles are employed. For the LPC, the 3-stage high speed axial compressor map presented in [48] is used and for the LPT the high speed, transonic, highly loaded 3-stage low pressure turbine map of [49] is selected. Finally, the Energy Efficient Engine maps for the 10-stage HPC reported in [50] and the 2-stage, cooled HPT of [51] are used for the corresponding HP spool components. The maps are extended and smoothed using the Smooth-C software [31] before converting them to the required PROOSIS map format. For both nozzles, the thrust coefficient is assumed fixed at all conditions while the discharge coefficient varies with nozzle pressure ratio.

Putting this model together creates a mathematical system containing approximately 3700 equations that requires two boundary variables; the handle and the variable geometry input signal value (VPF or VAN). Selecting the burner fuel-to-air ratio (FAR4) as handle, a non-linear system of equations is formed that requires initial values of all map auxiliary parameters, the engine inlet air flow rate $W1$ and BPR (eight algebraic variables in total). To solve this system (for a single operating point), these variables are iterated until corresponding residual equations are zeroed within a user-specified tolerance. These equations express mass flow continuity in all compressor, turbine and nozzle components. In addition, two linear equation systems exist (one for each spool). These linear systems express the torque balance requirement in each spool. Rotational speeds are dynamic variables (speed derivative appears in connecting shaft energy balance equations) which

mean that an initial guess is also required for each rotational speed variable. Hence, a 10x10 Jacobian matrix is formed (8 algebraic and 2 dynamic variables). This system is solved in PROOSIS with a modified Powell hybrid algorithm.

On this mathematical model of the UHBR engine configuration, a simulation case is defined containing an MPD structure with three operating points, namely take-off (TO), top-of-climb (ToC) and cruise (CR). Performance and installation requirements at these conditions come from top level aircraft requirements considering a commercial narrow body application with an EIS of 2025.

The mathematical model is extended to include the following independent variables (in addition to the model algebraic variables): the scaling factors of all the turbomachinery component maps, the HPT cooling flow fractions per stage row, the inlet and outlet component cross-sectional flow areas, the gearbox rotational speed ratio, the burner loading and the corrected mass flow for all ducts and the burner at design conditions¹. In addition, the two boundary variables, FAR4 and relevant variable geometry control signal (VAN or VPF) are also converted to unknowns. This creates the need for a total of 78 closure equations in addition to the model 30 internal closure equations (3 points · 10 algebraic variables). This means that 108 residues have to be evaluated. In the case of the two boundary variables, two additional closure equations are needed for each operating point. These are the required net thrust value FN at each operating point and an operability or performance target for the variable geometry signal value at TO only (for the other two points the signal is set to 0) such as the required bypass fan surge margin. With regards to the closure equations for establishing the other design variables, these are applied as follows: the location of the design (or reference) point on the maps is specified at ToC through setting the values of the map auxiliary parameters and corrected speed relative to design. Efficiency scaling factors are established by equating at CR conditions the cycle variables for fan/compressor polytropic efficiencies and turbine isentropic efficiencies to the corresponding ones in the aerodynamic design calculations. Mach number values at inlet and outlet of components are specified at ToC to establish the corresponding cross-sectional areas. Also at ToC, the design values for duct and burner pressure drop fractions and burner efficiency are specified. Metal temperatures for each HPT row are given at TO. Also at TO, two sets of inequalities are included, grouping the turbine blade stress parameter AN^2 (main equality) with upper bounding inequality constraints related to compressor first stage relative tip Mach number at ToC, compressor first and last stage tip blade speed and last stage compressor and turbine rim speed for both the LP and HP spools at TO. For the LP spool, an additional inequality is the maximum value of gearbox gear ratio. The remaining closure equations include specifying the values of OPR, FPR, pressure ratio split between the LP and HP compressors and fan corrected tip speed. These are defined at ToC with OPR being part of an inequality group that also includes the compressor exit temperature at TO and the compressor last stage blade height (LSBH) upper bounding inequalities. The final closure equation is the value for the nozzle ideal velocity ratio at CR. For this parameter, an optimization is performed within the MPD process so that the minimum value of uninstalled cruise SFC is obtained every time. As discussed by Kyprianidis and Rolt [52], the velocity ratio is preferred from BPR as design parameter since it relates directly to the transfer of power from the core to the bypass while for a given flight speed, FPR directly affects propulsive efficiency. No constraint has been placed on the maximum fan diameter.

For the simulations presented herein, fixed turbomachinery stage numbers are applied (1_G_3_8_2_3). LP and HP compressors are designed with the constant mean diameter option and assuming constant stage loading for the LPC and an enthalpy change distribution for the HPC. For the turbines, linear distribution of mean diameter is assumed with constant loading and symmetrical velocity diagram. For the HPT cooling model, the values corresponding to the advanced set of cooling technology factors in [39] are considered with the exception of the second stage rotor for which no film cooling is assumed. The combustion pattern factors are set to 0.1 and 0.05 for the first stage stator and rotor respectively and 0 for the second stage. No reduction to cooling air temperature due to pre-swirling is considered. The stage efficiency cooling correction factors are set to 0.1 and 0.2 for the stators and rotors respectively.

The effects of variable geometry on UHBR GTF engine performance and operability are exemplified in Figure 3. The figure presents the location of the three operating points on the fan bypass map for three different MPD simulations. In the first case (plot a), no variable geometry (VAN or VPF) is employed. For the second simulation (plot b), the VAN opens by 7.7% at take-off thus moving the point away from the surge line. In the last simulation, the VPF is used instead (no VAN). Closing the VPF at take-off by 4° (max value in current implementation) causes the map to shift as shown in plot c resulting again to an increase in surge margin

¹ In the current model, duct and burner pressure drop at off-design is expressed in terms of design pressure drop and corrected flow relative to the design value and burner efficiency is expressed in terms of burner loading relative to the design value.

compared to plot a. In both cases (VAN and VPF), the necessary change in variable geometry (nozzle area or pitch angle) is determined from a fixed fan surge margin requirement.

Figure 3 Location of operating points on fan bypass map for (a) no variable geometry employed (b) VAN opening at take-off by 7.7% from design point value and (c) VPF closing at take-off by 4°

Some indicative model results for the case of using the VPF version of the UHBR engine are presented in Table 1. The shaded cells in the table indicate design parameters. None of the constraints defined within the inequality groups are violated during this simulation.

Table 1
Model Results for VPF closing 4° at TO

Parameter	CR	TO	ToC	Parameter	CR	TO	ToC
Fan effPoly	0.955	0.960	0.959	Gear ratio		3.5	
LPC effPoly	0.913	0.910	0.906	NH (rpm)	19419	21567	20231
HPC effPoly	0.908	0.909	0.905	NLG (rpm)	2174	2413	2326
HPT eff	0.906	0.908	0.906	Tt3 (K)	780.8	947.4	845.9
LPT eff	0.921	0.915	0.922	Tt4 (K)	1576.4	1850.0	1731.9
FPR	1.299	1.296	1.35	Tt41 (K)	1532.3	1800.4	1683.2
LPC PR	2.52	2.53	2.64	Tt45 (K)	1127.0	1337.7	1245.8
HPR PR	14.7	14.1	15.6	Wcool/W3		9.84%	
HPT PR	4.21	4.19	4.20	HPT Work Potential		0.51	
LPT PR	9.35	7.75	9.63	HPT Tm S1 (K)	1134.9	1350.0	1240.8
OPR	44.2	42.2	50.0	HPT Tm R1 (K)	1047.2	1250.0	1144.4
BPR	19.64	17.97	18.51	HPT Tm S2 (K)	1136.1	1350.0	1246.4
W1 (kg/s)	286.4	678.3	290.7	HPT Tm R2 (K)	1046.5	1250.0	1149.2
VQid	0.75	0.69	0.68	Core Efficiency	0.549	0.506	0.560
Fan Dtip (m)		2.36		Propulsive Efficiency	0.814	0.529	0.791
Fan Ws (kg/(s·m ²))	195.7	170.3	203.1	Transfer Efficiency	0.829	0.833	0.849
HPC LSBH (mm)		13.16		SFC (g/(kN·s))	13.919	9.072	14.018
HPC Ws (kg/(s·m ²))	164.3	155.9	171.2	SFCinst (g/(kN·s))	16.554	9.375	16.203

The resultant fan tip diameter is 2.36 m while the HP compressor LSBH is above 13 mm. According to the cooling model assumptions, less than 10% of cooling flow (W_{cool}) needs to be extracted from the HPC exit to achieve at TO the specified HPT vane and blade metal temperatures (1350 and 1250 K respectively). The BPR at CR approaches a value of 20 for an optimum value of ideal nozzle velocity ratio VQ_{id} of 0.75. The uninstalled SFC at CR is 13.92 g/kN/s. When nacelle drag and engine weight are taken into account using the simplified approach presented in Section 2.5 this value increases to 16.55 g/kN/s. For the case of the VAN configuration, the different fan characteristics at take-off result to a different cycle matching affecting all three design points. Compared to the VPF case, the fan has lower pressure ratio (1.281) and polytropic efficiency (0.937) at TO but higher LPT isentropic efficiency (by ~1%) in all three operating points. This results to lower transfer efficiency at TO but higher at CR and ToC conditions, leading to improved SFC in these points by ~0.7%. In terms of total weight, the VPF configuration is estimated to be 3110 kg of which the LP system (Fan with PCM, LPC, LPT, gearbox and nacelle) accounts for 70% of the weight, the core ~6% and the structures

and controls the remaining 24%. The weight distribution is identical in the VAN case since the PCM weight of the VPF and the additional weight due to the VAN are estimated to be of similar magnitudes. As expected for this BPR level ([6], [15]), the VPF engine comes out lighter compared to the VAN one but only slightly (by ~35 kg) since the current weight estimation methodology lacks the fidelity needed to accurately capture the scalability benefits of the VPF concept.

An example of the design space created by parametric MPD runs is shown in Figure 4. Surface plots of uninstalled (plot a) and installed (plot b) SFC at CR are presented for ToC FPR varying between 1.25 and 1.45 and ToC OPR varying between 45 and 55. The parametric runs are performed for two values of allowable high pressure turbine metal temperature (T_m) at TO: 1200 and 1400 K (same for stators and rotors). For these runs, the VAN option is employed with the change in area established from the requirement for a fixed bypass fan map BETA value at TO. Minimum surge margin and maximum nozzle area constraints are also applied.

Figure 4 Surface plots of CR SFC as a function of ToC OPR and FPR for two values of TO HP turbine metal temperatures

When only engine performance is considered (plot a), the minimum SFC for the 1200 K case is 13.93 g/(kN·s) for FPR=1.29 and OPR=49. The corresponding BPR is 22. If the maximum allowable value of T_m is 1400 K then the minimum SFC reduces to 13.67 g/(kN·s) and occurs when FPR=1.31 and OPR=51 (BPR=23.3). This clearly demonstrates the potential benefits on engine performance from the use of advanced materials such as Ceramic Matrix Composites. In the first case, the cooling flow fraction ranges between 15 and 18% of HP compressor exit flow while in the second case it is between 4.7 and 4.9%. In both cases, the nozzle area at TO is greater than the ToC value by 9.5-24%. No constraints are violated in the lower temperature case but for the higher temperature one both the OPR (for values > 51) and HPT AN^2 (set to $32 \cdot 10^6 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{rpm}$) design parameters are restricted to lower values by the HPC LSBH (12.7 mm) and HPC last stage rim speed (400 m/s) constraints respectively due to the small core size and high shaft rotational speeds. When installation effects are taken into account (plot b), then minimum SFC (16.42 and 15.89 g/(kN·s) respectively) is obtained at the maximum value of FPR (1.45) but for different OPR values (46 for the low temperature case and 55 for the high temperature one). This is consistent with the remarks made earlier regarding the need for lightweight materials and slim low-drag nacelles in order to take full advantage of the low uninstalled SFC of UHBR engines.

Figure 5 demonstrates how the shape of the design space is affected when considering constant values for the efficiencies of turbomachinery components during the entire parametric sweep, as it is commonly done in many studies. Compared to the corresponding case where component efficiencies are obtained through aerodynamic calculations concurrently with cycle calculations for each combination of design parameters, a different distribution of CR SFC with ToC FPR and OPR is obtained. The absolute SFC values depend on the assumed values of the efficiencies which for the example presented here are selected to be close to those giving minimum CR SFC when using the integrated approach. So, the minimum SFC value is practically the same in both cases and it is located at the same value of FPR (1.29) but at the maximum value of OPR (55) in the simulation with constant component efficiencies since in this case thermal efficiency increases continuously with OPR. During the integrated procedure, the thermal efficiency exhibits a maximum with OPR increasing as the negative effect of increased component loading with OPR on component efficiencies (for fixed number of stages) is taken into account.

Figure 5 Surface plots of CR SFC as a function of ToC OPR and FPR using constant and calculated efficiency values

4.0 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, an integrated approach is presented combining at the same modelling level and within the same commercial simulation environment 0D thermodynamic with 1D aerodynamic calculations, flow path sizing and weight estimation. Suitable performance models of the variable geometry technologies considered for UHBR engines (VAN and VPF) have been developed. Design point efficiency of turbomachinery components is calculated according to component design choices and heuristic rules linking efficiency with design parameters. Empirical correlations are also used to estimate the weight of engine components. Installation effects are considered through a simplified approach correcting net thrust for nacelle drag and engine weight. A multi-point design methodology is then employed, allowing performance, aerodynamic and structural requirements and constraints to be met simultaneously at different operating points.

The capabilities developed are demonstrated by first constructing a generic UHBR GTF engine performance model. Parametric MPD simulations are then carried out considering the three main operating points in the commercial aircraft engine flight envelope (take-off, top-of-climb and cruise) for fixed thrust requirements and assuming different levels of turbine cooling technology.

The results depict the shape and limits of the feasible design space according to the specified performance targets and technological limits. Based on the assumptions and the range of design variables considered in this study, installation effects do not permit the SFC benefit of UHBR engines to be translated into fuel burn benefit. More detailed models for calculating engine weight and nacelle drag than the ones used in this study are required to determine the BPR/FPR values beyond which this conclusion applies. In addition, the presence of a gearbox oil cooler was not considered and this is expected to affect both uninstalled and installed performance. The assumptions regarding nozzle coefficients, especially in the case of a VAN configuration, are also expected to have an impact on overall engine performance. Another assumption that is expected to influence the results obtained is the constant bypass duct pressure drop since low FPR engines would see a lower bypass duct flow velocity. Finally, for fixed FPR and OPR values, the pressure ratio split between the LP and HP compressors and consequently the number of their stages can be specified as design parameters in order to take full advantage of the increased LP spool speed.

The work in this paper includes only some aspects of preliminary engine design but due to the flexibility and modularity of the current multi-disciplinary implementation framework it can be easily extended to include other modules such as emissions, noise, lifing and maintenance. The integration of an aircraft performance tool will then allow design space exploration and multidisciplinary optimisation assessments at aircraft mission level. Finally, the integrated procedure can be further developed to address operability aspects related to transient operation and control system definition.

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